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KEY SKILLS DEVELOPMENT IN INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In order to successfully shape a disruptive, volatile and digitized world, industrial engineers need (beyond their professional skills) methodological and social competencies more than ever. Scope of the research was to find out which competences, personality traits or value settings are essential for a successful career as Industrial Engineer (I.E.) particularly in a cross-functional working environment. Hence, engineering education has to find ways on how these competences can be developed during the BA/MA study programs? A qualitative research design was deliberately chosen. In total 50 I.E. experts from various backgrounds were interviewed in order to increase the understanding of the skills and competences required in a typical I.E. working environment. The results clearly highlight the importance of key competences for a successful professional as well as for a leadership career.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Industrial Engineering Education

Industrial Engineering education traces back to the late 19th century when selected American universities highlighted the need to bridge the gap between technical expert knowledge and economical expertise. Also in industry, professionals very often work in their field of specialisation without having a holistic overview of the whole “system”.

In Germany the first Industrial Engineering academic program started in 1927 at the Technischen Hochschule Berlin-Charlottenburg. Since then I.E. Education quickly evolved into a very relevant study program with more than 100 universities/ higher

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education institutions (Germany/ Austria/ Switzerland) offering IE study programs starting from Bachelor to PhD level.

1.2 Requirements for Industrial Engineering Education

Industrial Engineers are engineers with a solid foundation in economics as well as in social science. In their professional work they combine technical, social and economical aspects in a holistic way [1]. According to the national framework of the German Industrial Engineering Education association (VWI) the curricula should include more than 50% technical modules, at least 20% modules related to economics and business administration as well as minimum 10% integrative skills [2]. The professional working field of industrial engineers is very often in cross-functional settings. Statistics clearly indicate that approx. 75% of I.E. graduates pursue a management or leadership career.

1.3 Overcoming the skills mismatch

The higher education system is very much based on conveying expert knowledge in various fields. Undoubtedly this is a major prerequisite for success in the working environment. However, many investigations clearly indicate a mismatch between knowledge taught in tertiary education and industry requirements as shown in this figure:

Fig. 1. disparity between knowledge taught at universities and know-how required at workplace [2]

1.4 Scope & research questions

The scope of this investigation was guided by the following two research questions:

- Which competences, personality traits or value settings are essential for a successful career as an industrial engineer especially in a cross-functional working environment?
- How can these competences be fostered during a BA/MA I.E. study program?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Approach

The research is based on a literature review. Relevant publications especially from the Industrial Engineering Associations were investigated. Very often these investigations are based on questionnaires/ quantitative research.

However, for this study a qualitative research design was deliberately chosen. About fifty 1:1 interviews were conducted. From a methodical point of view, these were semi-structured, narrative interviews with the goal to better understand the perception of the experts. Average duration of each interview was about 50 minutes. A written consent form had to be signed by each partner. In addition an information sheet was given to each interview partner with a thorough description on how the material will be processed. Full anonymity was also assured. Each interview was recorded and fully transcribed.

2.2 Expert Selection/ Interview Partners

In total, fifty I.E. experts from various backgrounds were interviewed:

- Industrial engineers in top positions
- Industrial engineering senior lecturers
- Industrial engineering graduates

2.3 Data Processing & Evaluation using GABEK

GABEK ® [3] (Holistic Processing of Complexity) is a PC-supported method of qualitative research and text analysis (QDA). Based on open interviews or other verbal experiences, the knowledge and attitudes of many people are networked in order to acquire a well-founded overview. GABEK ® translates opinions of interview partners into termed knowledge systems. These systems provide a meaningful orientation for understanding the whole landscape of opinions. Every step of analysis can be interactively reconstructed and the results can be checked. For further information please see www.gabek.com.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Perception of experts

- The interviews clearly confirm that Industrial Engineers mainly work in cross functional settings
- Beyond the professional hard skills there is a clear challenge to interact with others in order to solve complex problems in an ever faster environment

- According to the interviewed experts the working environment can be described with the VUCA acronym [4]: volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous
- There is a need to build up intra-personal (“know yourself”) and inter-personal competences (ability to interact with others in multi-national/multi-functional settings)
- For a successful career a very strong attitude to perform seems to be essential
- Moreover situation-appropriate communication, problem-solving capabilities, willingness for lifelong-learning, network ability, ongoing reflective self-management, risk assessments and network-oriented thinking in addition to professional competences are essential success factors

3.2 Impact on Industrial Engineering Bachelor & Master Program

Based on research findings incl.literature [5] the current curriculum is under adaption. In general more problem & project based learning was included. Real life / business case studies are introduced. Further changes that are still under development were:

- Introduction of a lecture in systems engineering including also the usage of systemic question techniques
- Training the use of small group moderation, peer feedback, collegial advice for real life challenges
- Development of a presentation seminar including trainers with an actor`s background
- Introduction of business simulation games including Change-Management to experience team/group dynamics
- Development of monthly open lectures with industry experts from various field in a “Fire side chat setting”.
- Broadening the holistic view of students by including aspects related to the six PRiME principles (Principles of Responsible Management Education) including the 17 SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)
- Fostering the international perspective by offering a semester abroad & short term study tours
- Offering badges from university career center (beyond the traditional curriculum)
- Development of a mentoring system (graduates-students)

The underlying educational philosophy is based on a quote of former Management Expert Prof. Henry Mintzberg: Learning occurs where concept meets experience through reflection [6].

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